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Abstracts

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FunGlass

Structural study of binary alkaline-earth phosphate glasses by SVTD modeling and NMR and Raman spectroscopy

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Abstract

Over the past 100 years, different properties of phosphate glasses have been investigated for many different applications including a variety of industrial applications, high power lasers, nuclear waste hosts, specialty hermetic seals etc. These properties are related to the structure of glass. The structural study of various phosphate glasses is of paramount importance. Usually, solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), X-ray absorption (XAS), and neutron diffraction analysis provide unprecedented detail of the bonding arrangements in glasses. Shakhmatkin and Vedishcheva proposed an associated solutions thermodynamic model (SVTD) that has been successfully applied for describing the structure of silicate, phosphate and chalcogenide glasses. The aim of the present work is the determination of the structure of glasses of the binary systems P2O5-MgO, and P2O5-BaO with different amounts of modifiers (BaO and MgO) by comparison of SVTD model with the results of MAS NMR. By using SVTD model, MgO, and BaO dependence of equilibrium molar amounts of the system components at a fixed temperature was calculated. Three pseudo-binary regions for MgO & BaO systems in the glass forming region (content up to 58 mol % of modifiers) were identified. Raman spectra were measured for all glasses and analyzed them by Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Multivariate Curve Resolution (MCR) and spectral decomposition by the method of Malfait. PCA method identifies the number of independent components in the studied spectral series. On the other hand, the number of independent components with significant abundance in the studied glasses was obtained by from thermodynamic modeling. Partial Raman spectra of independent components were calculated using the method of Malfait. The MCR method has been used for the analysis of the experimental spectra to find the spectra of pure components (so-called loadings) and the relative abundances of these components (so-called scores). Moreover, glass characteristics, such as